

Strength distributions of silicon devices determined by wafer backgrinding

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The effects of wafer backgrinding on the strength of silicon devices in the form of dies are investigated experimentally and analytically. In particular, the scale and orientation of striations generated by in-feed grinding on wafer and die back faces are shown to be critical factors in determining the spatial arrangement of die strengths over a wafer and the strength distributions of dies sampled from a wafer. The scale of the striations is considered in the context of controlled indentation and scratch flaw experiments, leading to the assessment that strength-controlling grinding striations are formed by translated sharp contacts with approximately 0.1 N normal load. The effect of striation orientation is described by a simple expression fit to experimental die strength measurements. An analytical formulation of striation orientation based on in-feed grinding geometry parameters implements the expression to generate wafer strength maps and sample strength distributions. The maps and distributions are of direct engineering applicability.

1. Introduction

1.1. Semiconductor device fabrication

Semiconductor device fabrication may be divided into four sequential stages: two electrical, followed by two mechanical. In the first, electrical, stage, known as front end of line (FEOL), dopants are implanted into or deposited onto the surface of a large circular wafer of semiconducting material—usually single crystal silicon (Si). The dimensions of wafers used in fabrication currently are predominantly 300 mm diameter \times 775 μm thick or, less commonly, 200 mm \times 725 μm , and all are oriented such that the wafer face is the Si(001) plane. The wafer is the substrate for the many billions of discrete electrical circuit elements formed in the Si during FEOL processing. In the second electrical stage, known as back end of line (BEOL), successive layers of conductors and insulators are deposited and patterned over the wafer surface to form a three-dimensional array interconnecting the individual circuit elements. BEOL processing generates very large scale integrated (VLSI) circuits forming individual devices over the wafer surface in a rectangular array aligned along Si \langle 110 \rangle directions, Fig. 1(a). After completion of the FEOL and BEOL stages, the VLSI devices are tested for quality and a “wafer map” of electrical performance of the devices is generated.

Figure 1. Front and back faces of a 200 mm Si wafer at various stages during semiconductor device fabrication. (a) Front face of full 725 μm thickness wafer after electrical circuit formation into a rectangular array of VLSI devices. (b) Back face of full thickness wafer; interference colors indicate films residual from VLSI processing. (c) Back face of 420 μm thick wafer after first, Z1, coarse stage of backgrinding; wafer surface is matte and grinding striations are evident. (d) Back face of 380 μm thick wafer after second, Z2, fine stage of backgrinding; wafer surface generates specular reflection.

The third, mechanical, stage is known as wafer finishing. In this stage, material is removed from the Si wafer substrate in two sub-stages: backgrinding and dicing. In the backgrinding sub-stage, material is removed uniformly from the back (non-device) face of the

wafer, Fig. 1(b), parallel to the wafer surface, to generate a substrate of appropriate thickness and back face surface finish. Usually the majority of material is removed by a coarse rotating grinding wheel operation, known as Z1, leaving residual surface and sub-surface damage in the wafer back face, Fig. 1(c). Hence, back face surface treatments are often completed by fine grinding, known as Z2, Fig. 1(d), or chemically assisted etching or polishing. In the next substage, dicing, material is locally removed from the front (device) side of the wafer, perpendicular to the wafer surface, to generate dies of appropriate length and width. Usually material is removed in this substage by a rotating dicing saw blade that penetrates the entire thinned wafer perpendicular to the wafer surface. The blade is translated along Si⟨110⟩ directions, between the devices defined in the FEOL and BEOL stages. After dicing, the now individual or singulated devices are sorted and picked using the electrical wafer map generated after the BEOL stage. In the fourth stage, known as packaging, the thinned, rectangular, sorted and picked devices (or “chips”) are attached mechanically and electrically to larger metallic, polymeric, or ceramic substrates, and encapsulated to form packaged devices suitable for use in electronic applications, for example in hand-held tablets, cell phones, and smart cards.

1.2. Wafer backgrinding and die strength

The focus of the work here is mechanical performance of devices determined by the third and fourth fabrication stages above, rather than the more commonly studied electrical performance determined by the first two stages. The focus is a consequence of the significant commercial driving force for fabrication and use of thinned dies. Smaller and thinner dies enable greater density of devices in applications and thus greater application functionality, *e.g.*, through more chips/cell phone. In addition, thinned devices enable reduced power consumption through fewer parasitic electrical and thermal effects, and are critical to new high density packaging schemes, such as stacked dies. Hence, mechanical backgrinding is likely to remain an essential part of the semiconductor fabrication process: the diversity of consequent challenges generated by thinned wafers and dies in semiconductor fabrication and application is reviewed by Marks *et al.* [2015]. The current work will consider a specific challenge in detail—the mechanical strength of dies limited by backgrinding damage, Figs. 1(c) and (d). Such strengths determine device yield in the fabrication stages of dicing, sorting, picking, and packaging, and determine packaged device reliability in operation. During fabrication, die mechanical strengths limit the loads that can be applied to dies (*e.g.*, by robotic handling devices). During operation, die mechanical strengths limit the thermal expansion mismatch stresses that can be applied to dies by packaging materials, (*e.g.*, polymer circuit boards) and limit the stresses that can be applied to dies by users (*e.g.*, by bending of a credit card). Hence, in order to optimize semiconductor device fabrication

a wafer map of die mechanical strength is required, similar to that generated for die electrical performance.

A common grinding process that determines die strength is “in-feed” grinding. In this process, the abrasive face of a rapidly rotating circular wheel is used to remove material from the back face of a semiconductor wafer. Material removal is facilitated by small, sharp, hard particles (diamonds, alumina, silicon carbide) imbedded in the abrasive face of the grinding wheel. The wheel diameter is less than that of the wafer, and the wheel and wafer axes, although parallel, are not co-linear. A schematic diagram is shown in Fig. 2. In operation, the wafer is rotated slowly about the wafer axis while the rapidly rotating grinding wheel is simultaneously translated parallel to the wheel axis slowly “into” the wafer. In this way, the grinding wheel center describes a helical path relative to the wafer center and the grinding wheel face removes material from the entire wafer back face, Fig. 1(c).

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of wafer back face in-feed grinding process. The rotations of the wafer, large disc fixed to underlying chuck, and grinding wheel, small disc fixed to spindle, about their respective axes are indicated by open arrows. The linear motion of the grinding wheel center “in” towards the wafer is indicated by the solid arrow.

In-feed grinding generates surface damage as an array of striations in the form of circular arcs radiating from the wafer center. As a geometrical consequence, the striations exhibit a systematic orientation variation over the back face of the wafer, Fig. 3, and thus from die to die. The striations are residual plastic deformation and fracture tracks generated by individual abrasive particles translated in contact with the wafer surface. The strength controlling nature of these striations in terms of orientation relative to a die edge and subsequent package orientation is the focus of the current work.

Figure 3. Optical micrographs of the back face of a Z1 ground wafer. The overall wafer view from Fig. 1(c) is shown along with five images illustrating different orientations of near-parallel grinding striations in different locations on the wafer back face. Z1 + Z2 grinding striations are similarly oriented.

Specifically, the following sections demonstrate the generation of wafer-scale maps of die mechanical strength, and consequent strength distributions, as controlled by in-feed grinding. First, brief overviews are given of prior observations of linear flaws in Si surfaces, single scratches and multiple striations. Next, experimental measurements of strengths of Si dies are presented, using controlled flaws to characterize strengths. The observations and measurements are placed in the context of linear contact flaw analyses [Cook, 2017, 2018] and provide background for the principal section of the current work that follows—the development of a model to predict die strength maps and distributions using in-feed grinding parameters and experimental strength measurements. The basis of the model is outlined in two earlier patents [Mendelson *et al.*, 1999, 2001] and several recent works considering the linkages between flaw population and sampled strength distributions [Cook and DelRio, 2019ab; Cook *et al.*, 2019, 2020; DelRio *et al.*, 2020]. The strength distributions of dies resulting from in-feed wafer backgrinding are compared with those resulting from strength measurements of Si microelectromechanical systems (MEMS), bulk ceramics, and small particles [Cook and DelRio, 2019ab; Cook *et al.*, 2019, 2020; DelRio *et al.*, 2020].

2. Linear flaws in Si

2.1. Single scratches

The fracture mechanics of strength controlling linear flaws is reviewed and developed in detail in two recent works [Cook 2017, 2018]. The works consider large-scale features formed by dragged or rolling contacts on ceramics, glasses, semiconductors, and other brittle materials, and make a clear distinction between such linear flaws and the more frequently studied point-like sharp indentation flaws. An important finding to emerge from these works is that extended striations or scratches are much more potent as strength-degrading surface flaws than localized contacts. The normal load required to generate a strength-controlling striation or scratch flaw by a translated sharp contact is about 0.1 N or less, whereas the load required to generate a strength-controlling impact or indentation flaw by the same sharp contact at normal incidence is about 1 N or greater. The nature of the damage leading to strength-controlling striations is shown in the schematic diagram of Fig. 4, which depicts two sharp particles translated over a brittle material surface at small, slightly different, normal loads. In both cases, the translated particle generates a striation in the form of a residually deformed, linear surface impression (shown as light shading). Beneath each striation is a localized, near semi-cylindrical, zone of plastic deformation (shown in section as dark shading). Compressive strain in the localized plastic deformation zone generates a tensile residual stress field in the surrounding elastically-deformed matrix. If the striation is of sufficient size, the residual field can initiate and stabilize cracks in the matrix adjacent to the plastic deformation zone. In particular, a crack is shown beneath the zone for the slightly larger striation, Fig. 4(b). Such a crack, formed centrally beneath the zone, perpendicular to the surface, is known as a median crack, and the striation-crack combination is termed a “post threshold flaw” as the threshold conditions for crack initiation, such as normal load and particle acuity, are exceeded. The slightly smaller striation, Fig. 4(a), is termed a “sub threshold flaw” as the threshold conditions for crack initiation are not exceeded. Under the action of a superposed applied stress, a large striation forming a post threshold flaw is often strength controlling through the ensuing instability and propagation of the median crack leading to component failure. Small striations can also be strength controlling, as an applied stress can “pop-in” a median crack at a sub threshold flaw, leading to immediate instability, crack propagation, and failure.

As will be shown below, the strength-controlling damage generated by backgrinding Si wafers most probably consists of multiple sub threshold linear contact flaws. That is, multiple, curved versions of Fig. 4(a). Early, 1980s, research on linear damage in Si, however, considered single post threshold flaws generated by translated contacts with large normal loads, typically

greater than 0.25 N. The focus was on damage morphology: Such flaws exhibited significant lateral cracking, chipping, and material removal parallel to the surface, in addition to the surface impression and sub-surface median crack of Fig. 4(b), and were more aptly described as scribe lines or scratches. A cross-section illustrating the impression and distinct lateral and median cracks at a scribe line in Si [Misra and Finnie, 1979] is very similar to that of a glass-cutting roller track [Howes and Szameitat, 1984]. Much more surface damage and material removal is visible in images of scratches in Si generated by a sharp probe [Lim and Danyluk, 1985, 1988; Danyluk *et al.*, 1988]. An early study of damage generated by translated blunt probes on Si [Leu and Scattergood, 1988] showed that much greater contact loads were required, ≈ 100 N, and that the damage morphology was significantly different and dominated by near-surface circular chatter cracks. These observations of flaws formed on Si surfaces by large-load scribing or scratching provide extreme upper bounds to the extent of damage generated by backgrinding.

Figure 4. Schematic diagrams of linear flaws generated in surfaces by translated sharp contacts. The top view shows the contact and the ensuing plastic deformation track (light shading). The cross-section view shows the sub-surface plastic deformation zone (dark shading). (a) Small, sub-threshold contact load. (b) Large, post threshold contact load exhibiting larger plastic deformation track and zone and sub-surface median crack (dashed line).

2.2. Multiple striations

Subsequent research, in the early 1990s–2000s, on linear damage in Si did consider the effects of typical backgrinding flaws on the strength of Si wafers and dies. The two-fold motivation for this consideration was (i) the introduction of larger wafers that were more susceptible to both failure during handling and grinding-induced dimensional non-uniformities [Bawa *et al.*, 1995; Mendelson *et al.*, 1996]; and (ii) the introduction of polymeric-based packaging schemes that placed the die in tension and thus generated a greater likelihood of package-induced device failure [Michaelides and Sitaraman, 1999; Yu *et al.*, 2002]. A review of sharp contact damage and fracture strength of Si summarized the research findings regarding the backgrinding-strength linkage [Cook, 2006]: After front face processing, the back faces of Si wafers, Fig. 1(b), are reasonably strong (≈ 200 MPa), although not as strong as MEMS devices (≈ 2 GPa); coarse backgrinding, Fig. 1(c), reduces this strength for Si dies considerably (≈ 50 MPa); subsequent fine backgrinding, Fig. 1(d), restores the strength to the wafer level or greater (≈ 300 MPa); final stage etching can increase the strengths even more, nearly to MEMS levels. The qualitative trends in Si strength during wafer finishing were identified in an early work addressing the backgrinding-strength linkage [Hudson and Perrin, 1990]. Subsequent research led to the quantitative findings above and to recognition of the different effects on the Si surface of the various wafer finishing steps. As summarized by Marks *et al.* [2015]: Coarse grinding, designated Z1, performs the greatest reduction in wafer thickness (and thus removes the majority of water material), hundreds of micrometers at approximately $5 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$, and generates an optically rough surface, rms roughness of several micrometers, and significant sub-surface damage, tens of micrometers in depth. Fine grinding, designated Z2, reduces the surface roughness, removing material at approximately $1 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$, to generate an optically smooth surface, rms roughness of several nanometers, and removes sub-surface damage. An optional polishing step, designated Z3, continues these processes at a finer level. Final etching is designed to reduce the surface roughness to sub-nanometer levels and remove even more subsurface damage. Both polishing and etching involve significant chemical effects.

More detailed research regarding Si die strength, in the late 1990s–late 2000s, focused on Z1 backgrinding parameters. The Z1 step generates the greatest surface roughness and largest amount of sub-surface damage and is therefore the most strength-controlling. Two extensive studies in 1997 identified most of the important phenomena regarding the geometrical linkages between wafer backgrinding and die strength. Lee *et al.* [1997] found that: (i) the striations generated by in-feed backgrinding formed an array of curved arcs radiating from the center of the wafer; (ii) a die picked from the wafer exhibited nearly parallel striations, oriented relative to the die axes in a direction that depended on die location within the wafer, Fig. 3; and (iii) the

most significant factor in determining die strength was striation orientation relative to the die axes. In particular, for uniaxial flexure tests in which the long axis of a rectangular die was in tension, strength was significantly greater for dies exhibiting striations more closely aligned with the long axis. A schematic diagram of an in feed ground wafer back face and example grinding striations and die locations are shown in Fig. 5(a). McGuire *et al.* [1997] used a Z1 variation known as “creep feed” grinding, in which the wafer is translated, rather than rotated, beneath the grinding wheel, and found that: (i) the striations generated formed a parallel array of curved arcs across the wafer back face; (ii) a die picked from the wafer exhibited parallel striations oriented relative to the die axes in a direction that depended most strongly on wafer orientation relative to the creep feed direction; and (iii) in equi-biaxial flexure tests, in which the entire face of a square die was placed in isotropic tension, there was no significant effect on strength of striation orientation relative to the die axes, implying that the strength controlling striation damage was not location dependent. Cross-section measurements showed the grinding damage to extend 15 μm beneath the surface and an inverse correlation was demonstrated between damage depth and strength. A schematic diagram of a creep feed ground wafer back face and example grinding striations and die locations are shown in Fig. 5(b).

Figure 5. Schematic diagrams of wafer back faces with representative examples of grinding striations and dies. (a) In feed striations and rectangular dies. Uniaxial strength tests exhibit a significant effect of die location. (b) Creep feed striations and squares dies. Biaxial strength tests exhibit no significant effect of die orientation.

Two patents by Mendelson *et al.* [1999, 2001] placed the backgrinding-strength linkage on sound quantitative experimental and analytical foundations, and generated clear design bounds for grinding parameters to meet specified strength requirements. Mendelson *et al.* determined analytical expressions for the shape of striation arrays formed by in-feed, creep-feed, and other back grinding geometries and provided expressions for experimentally determined variations of strength with striation orientation. Combining the analyses with the measurements enabled quantitative strength bounds to be established along with clear qualitative descriptions of strength behavior as systems deviated from optimum grinding parameters (*e.g.*, grinding wheel diameter relative to die size). [The intent of the work here is to extend the patents of Mendelson *et al.* by providing (i) greater insight into, and better descriptions of, strength behavior with regard to grinding-induced flaws; and (ii) complete descriptions of strength behavior beyond the bounding values, including spatial variations and distributions.]

An extensive series of studies by Pei and colleagues [Pei *et al.*, 1999; Pei and Strasbaugh, 2001, 2002; Pei, 2002; Chidambaram *et al.*, 2003ab; Sun *et al.*, 2004, 2005ab; Pei *et al.*, 2005; Pei *et al.*, 2008], while not considering strength, explored the technology and damage phenomenology of in-feed grinding in detail. In particular: Pei *et al.* [1999] showed striation cross sections with median cracks extending to about 20 μm beneath the surface, similar in form to those in Fig. 4(b) and in the earlier observations of somewhat greater damage by Misra and Finnie [1979] and Howes and Szameitat [1984]; Pei [2002] and Pei and Strasbaugh [2002] used Makyoh (“magic mirror”) techniques to show images of backgrinding striation patterns on wafers as an array of radiating circular arcs, similar to those described by Lee *et al.* [1997], Fig. 5(a); Chidambaram *et al.* [2003b] developed a mathematical model to describe and predict the shape of the grinding striation arrays as a function of grinding parameters. The model was in agreement with the earlier observations [Lee *et al.*; Pei, 2002; Pei and Strasbaugh, 2002] and similar to that developed earlier by Mendelson *et al.* [1999, 2001]; Sun *et al.* [2005b] developed a model for the depth variation of the striations, resulting in depths between 0.2 μm and 0.4 μm . This model was in agreement with single-point ductile turning observations that showed that the transition in Si from the sub-threshold flaw configuration, Fig. 4(a), to the post threshold configuration, Fig. 4(b), occurred at an impression or striation depth between 0.2 μm and 1 μm [Chao *et al.*, 2002]. In addition, the values were consistent with Raman measurements of a heavily deformed surface layer developed on Si backgrinding, thickness of approximately 0.5 μm [Chen and de Wolf, 2003], etching studies of removal of a heavily stressed layer (relieving Si wafer bow), thickness of approximately 0.6 μm [Haapalinna *et al.*, 2004], and measurements and modeling of grinding striation depths of the related SiC ceramic, between 0.1 and 0.5 μm [Agarwal and Rao, 2010].

Many additional, explicit strength studies reinforced the idea that uniaxial die strengths depended on backgrinding striation orientation [Wu *et al.*, 2003; Chong *et al.*, 2004; McLellan *et al.*, 2004; Dries *et al.*, 2008; Zhao *et al.*, 2009; Chae *et al.*, 2010]. Specifically, that striations parallel to the tensile axis applied in strength testing (usually by bending along the long axis of a die) led to the greatest strengths and striations perpendicular to the tensile axis led to the weakest strengths, as illustrated in Fig. 5(a). As the die location on the wafer determined the striation orientation, there was a clear correlation between die strength and location, *e.g.*, as shown in Chao *et al.* [2010]. In addition, many studies reinforced the idea that die strengths increased significantly if the striations were diminished or removed by fine grinding or etching of the wafer back face, or if the front face was tested [Liu *et al.*, 2002; Cotterell *et al.*, 2003; Jeong *et al.*, 2004; Funke *et al.*, 2004; Yoshikawa *et al.*, 2012; Watanabe *et al.*, 2014]. In these cases, the correlation between die strength and location was diminished or lost, as observed earlier by McGuire *et al.* [1997]. Measurements of the total damage depth created by backgrinding were in the range of 15 μm to 30 μm [Jeong *et al.*, 2004; Yoshikawa *et al.*, 2012; Watanabe *et al.*, 2014], and it was recognized that not all damage was removed by etching.

In summary, the above observations provide physical bases and semi-quantitative descriptions of backgrinding controlled die strength. However, a fully predictive strength model requires experimental measurements and quantitative descriptions of the variations in die strength with flaw size and striation orientation. The following section presents such strength measurements and descriptions.

3. Strength of Si

3.1. Controlled flaws

Figure 6 shows optical microscope images of the back face of a Si wafer processed by in-feed Z1 + Z2 grinding and containing subsequently introduced controlled flaws. The flaws were generated by a sharp Vickers indenter, either by conventional indentation contact perpendicular to the wafer surface and are indicated by arrows in (a) and (b), or by Vickers contact and scratching parallel to the surface adjacent to a broken edge (left) of the wafer, (c) and (d). Details of indentation and scratching can be found elsewhere [Cook, 2017]. The back face parallel grinding striations, approximately 2 μm in width, are clear and oriented slightly diagonally in the images.

Figure 6. Optical micrographs of Z1 + Z2 ground wafer back faces showing parallel arrays of grinding striations and introduced indentations (indicated by arrows) and scratch flaws. (a) 0.1 N normal Vickers indentation. (b) 1 N normal Vickers indentation. (c) 0.1 N Vickers indentation scratch. (d) 1 N Vickers indentation scratch.

The indentation in Fig. 6(a) was formed with a contact load of $P = 0.1$ N and is barely visible within the striation array at this magnification. The indentation scale is consistent with earlier measurements [Cook, 2006] that showed the dimensions of the surface impression at this load are approximately $2\ \mu\text{m}$ to $3\ \mu\text{m}$ and the surface traces of any associated cracks are approximately $3\ \mu\text{m}$ to $5\ \mu\text{m}$. As the indentation surface damage in Fig. 6(a) is comparable in size to the visible striations, the $P = 0.1$ N indentation load thus provides a likely lower bound to the contacts required to generate strength-controlling flaws on a ground surface. The indentation in Fig. 6(b) was formed with an indentation load of $P = 1$ N and the square indentation contact impression and surface traces of cracks radiating from the impression corners are clearly visible; the dimensions are consistent with the earlier measurements of $10\ \mu\text{m}$ to $15\ \mu\text{m}$ for the impression dimensions and $20\ \mu\text{m}$ to $30\ \mu\text{m}$ for the cracks. The indentation surface damage in Fig. 6(b) is larger than the grinding striations and could thus most probably constitute a strength controlling flaw and reduce the wafer strength from the level set by the grinding striations. In engineering context, the indentation loads used to generate the flaws in Figs. 6(a) and (b) bracket the gravitational force exerted by the mass of the wafer. The mass of a 200 mm diameter wafer is about 50 g, leading to about 0.5 N weight; about 1.2 N weight for a 300 mm wafer. Hence, simply placing a wafer on a sharp particle under its own weight is enough to generate a flaw greater in size than the grinding damage.

The linear flaw in Fig. 6(c) was formed with a normal contact load of 0.1 N, as in Fig. 6(a), but the indenter was translated at approximately $0.5\ \text{mm s}^{-1}$ from right to left over the wafer surface and off the wafer edge. The resulting flaw consists of a linear impression with adjacent fine debris and closely resembles the ideal linear contact flaws of Fig. 4 and the observations of Danyluk *et al.* [1988], Misra and Finnie [1997], and Chao *et al.* [2002]. No surface cracks are visible and as the sub-surface is not visible it is not possible to ascertain if the flaw exhibits a sub- or post-threshold configuration. The edge appears to only weakly perturb the flaw as indicated by the appearance of slightly more debris. The width of the track in Fig. 6(c) is approximately $10\ \mu\text{m}$ and it is clear that the damage generated is far greater than that generated in Fig. 6(a) and much larger than the grinding striations and could thus constitute a strength controlling flaw. In fact, the implication of Fig. 6(c) is that linear flaws formed by much smaller normal contact loads, as the grinding striations appear to have been, could be strength controlling. The flaw in Fig. 6(d) was formed with a normal contact load of 1 N, as in Fig. 6(b), but the indenter was translated over the wafer surface and off the wafer edge as in Fig. 6(c). The resulting flaw consists of a barely discernible plastic deformation track covered by significant amount of coarse debris formed from fragments and cracked material. Surface lateral cracks adjacent to the track are clear suggesting the existence of a sub-surface median crack as in Fig. 4(b). The flaw resembles the scratch observations of Lim and Danyluk [1985, 1988]. The edge

significantly perturbs the flaw as indicated by the generation of more cracking and debris. The scratch damage in Fig. 6(d) is approximately 50 μm in extent, much larger than that generated in Fig. 6(b) and the grinding striations and thus easily constitutes a strength controlling flaw.

Figure 7 shows the strength σ of back face ground Si dies, 15.5 mm length \times 6.9 mm width \times 370 μm thick, tested in four point bending along the length. Details of strength testing can be found elsewhere [Cook, 2017]. The die back faces were Z1 + Z2 in-feed ground and many contained an introduced controlled indentation or scratch flaw as described above, Fig. 6. Fig. 7 is thus a strength degradation plot in logarithmic coordinates: filled symbols represent indentation-strength measurements at the loads P indicated; open symbols represent scratch strength measurements at the normal contact loads indicated; individual symbols represent individual strength measurements; uncertainty bars represent the mean and standard deviation limits for at least five measurements; and the shaded band represents the mean and standard deviation limits of approximately 35 as-ground dies selected randomly from several wafers.

Figure 7. Indentation strength degradation plot for Si dice containing introduced indentation or scratch flaws at the normal contact loads indicated. Symbols represent strength measurements, lines represent ideal contact mechanics responses appropriate to Si, Shaded band indicates intrinsic strength range determined by grinding.

The maximum strength level in Fig. 7 is set by the as-ground dies, 282 ± 52 MPa. The strength is decreased or degraded by the introduction of controlled flaws, more so by the linear scratches than by the indentations. The upper line in Fig. 7 is of slope $-1/3$, describing a $P^{-1/3}$ dependence of strength on indentation load characteristic of indentation flaws, and quantified by $\sigma P^{1/3} = 130$ MPa N^{1/3} typical for single crystal Si [Cook, 2006]. This line intersects the as-ground strength level at an indentation load of $P = 0.1$ N, suggesting that indentation-like sharp contact flaws of this magnitude could describe the strength-controlling element of the grinding damage. This assessment is consistent with the observations of Fig. 6 that showed that 0.1 N indentation flaws were comparable in scale to the grinding striations (a) and that 1 N indentation flaws were larger than the grinding striations (b). The lower line in Fig. 7 is of slope $-1/2$, describing a $P^{-1/2}$ dependence of strength on indentation load characteristic of scratch flaws [Cook, 2017], and quantified by $\sigma P^{1/2} = 28$ MPa N^{1/2}. This line intersects the as-ground strength at an indentation load of $P = 0.01$ N, suggesting that scratch-like sharp contact flaws of this magnitude could describe the strength-controlling element of the grinding damage. This assessment is consistent with the observation of Fig. 6(c) that showed that 0.1 N scratch flaws were larger in scale than the grinding striations. The assessment is also consistent with earlier work on alumina that showed that linear flaw strengths were shifted by approximately a factor of ten to smaller contact loads relative to indentation strengths [Cook, 2017].

Figure 7 implies that the Z1 + Z2 resultant grinding flaws can be characterized as sharp contacts by loads between 0.01 N, for translated contacts as in Fig. 4, and 0.1 N, for static contacts as by indentations. These values are in quantitative agreement with earlier work on Si [Cook, 2006] and linear flaws [Cook, 2017]. Another point of quantitative agreement is with independent measurement of the toughness of Si, $T = 0.75$ MPa m^{1/2} [Cook, 2006]. Assuming the flaws are simple Griffith cracks, a characteristic crack length c can be estimated from $c = (T/\psi\sigma)^2$, where ψ is a geometrical constant, here taken as $\psi = 1.5$ appropriate to linear surface cracks. Using these values gives $c \approx 3$ μm , consistent with the observations, Fig. 6, of the grinding striations. Overall, in the context of strength-controlling flaws, Figs. 6 and 7 provide a self-consistent quantitative description of the scale of grinding damage that is also consistent with independent measurements of Si properties and behavior. The next section extends consideration of Si die strength beyond the *scale* of the strength-controlling flaws to *flaw orientation*.

3.2. Grinding flaws

Figure 8 shows the strength σ of Z1 or Z1 + Z2 back-face ground Si dies measured in four-point bending along the length of the die. A range of die dimensions similar to those stated

above were measured. The strength test geometry is characterized by the angle θ between the long edge of the die and the direction of striations on the die back face, defined in the schematic diagram in Fig. 8. During testing, the back face of a die is placed in uniaxial tension along the die length and therefore θ is also the angle between the striations and the tensile axis. Symbols and bars in Fig. 8 represent the experimental means and standard deviation limits of at least five strength measurements under the conditions specified at the angle θ indicated. Individual strength measurements under the conditions specified at the angle θ indicated. Individual symbols represent individual strength measurements; for clarity, some symbols are displaced.

Figure 8. Variations of uniaxial strength with striation orientation for Si dies. Symbols represent strength measurements for dies with striations at the orientation angle indicated. Lines represent best fits of empirical polynomial between maximum and minimum strength bounds, Eq. (1). (a) Z1 grinding and Z1 + Z2 depth study. (b) Z1 + Z2 grit study. Schematic diagram shows definition of θ .

Figure 8(a) shows the variation of strength with striation orientation for two different back-face grinding conditions, Z1 and Z1 + Z2. The strength measurements are consistent with the observations noted in section 2.2: The strengths of Z1 ground dies are considerably less than those of Z1 + Z2 ground dies, for all values of θ . For both conditions, the strength is a maximum for striations parallel to the long edge of the dies, $\theta = 0^\circ$, and significantly reduced to a minimum for striations perpendicular to the long edge, $\theta = 90^\circ$. The observed variation of strength with orientation can be described by

$$\sigma = \sigma_{\max} - (\sigma_{\max} - \sigma_{\min})[2(\theta/90)^3 - 3(\theta/90)^2], \quad (1)$$

where θ is expressed in degrees and σ_{\max} and σ_{\min} are empirical fitting parameters characterizing upper and lower bounds of strength, respectively. Equation (1) provides a slightly better smooth continuous description of the experimental observations and is more easily implemented analytically than the piece-wise description used earlier [Mendelson, 1999, 2000; Cook, 2017]. The solid lines in Fig. 8 are visual best fits of Eq. (1) to the strength data: $\sigma_{\max} = 150$ MPa and $\sigma_{\min} = 50$ MPa for the Z1 ground dies in Fig. 8(a). Comparison with Fig. 7 suggests that the Z1 grinding flaws in Fig. 8(a) correspond to striations formed with normal contact load of about 0.3 N.

Three sets of Z1 + Z2 ground die strengths are also shown in Fig. 8(a). All sets were identically Z1 ground but were subsequently Z2 ground so as to remove three different thicknesses of material, 20 μm , 40 μm , and 60 μm . There was no significant effect on strength of Z2 thickness reduction. The strength invariance has two implications: that the initial 20 μm reduction removed the Z1 surface damage layer, consistent with the earlier estimates cited above, and that the initial reduction introduced a layer of Z2 damage that remained invariant with increasing Z2 grinding. For all thickness reductions, the Z2 strengths exhibited a clear increase in dispersion with decreasing θ , implying that there was greater variability in the strength-controlling nature of the grinding flaws as striations approached orientations more closely aligned with die edges. The best fit of Eq. (1) to the Z1 + Z2 strength data in Fig. 8(a) provides $\sigma_{\max} = 450$ MPa and $\sigma_{\min} = 150$ MPa.

Figure 8(b) shows many of the same trends in strength variation with striation orientation for four different Z1 + Z2 back-face grinding sets. As above the sets were identically Z1 ground; in this case subsequent Z2 grinding using different abrasive grit sizes. Similar to the above, the strengths are considerably greater than those of Z1 ground dies for all values of θ , with maxima for striations parallel to the long edge of the dies and minima for striations perpendicular to the long edge. The strengths are described by Eq. (1) using $\sigma_{\max} = 260$ MPa and $\sigma_{\min} = 90$ MPa as shown by the solid line. There was no significant effect on strength of Z2 grit size implying that all grits used removed the Z1 surface damage approximately equally, although perhaps not as

effectively as in Fig. 8(a). In addition, there was an increase in the strength dispersion with decreasing θ for all grits. Comparison with Fig. 7 suggests that the Z2 grinding flaws in Figs. 8(a) and 8(b) correspond to striations formed with normal contact loads between 0.03 N and 0.1 N.

The uniaxial strength measurements shown in Fig. 8 are in agreement with previous observations of the effects of back grinding striation severity and orientation (section 2.2) and with the current flaw size estimations and strength degradation measurements (Figs. 6 and 7). The quantitative description of striation orientation effects on uniaxial strength, Eq. (1) and solid lines in Fig. 8, is a key element of model development in subsequent sections. Before such development, additional *biaxial* strength measurements will be considered, providing both further agreement with previous observations and insight into model interpretation.

Figure 9. Plot of biaxial strength vs uniaxial strength for Si dies measured using square and rectangular specimens with a range of back face surface finishes. Biaxial strengths are systematically greater than uniaxial strengths.

Figure 9 shows measurements of Si biaxial strength as a function of die uniaxial strength for a variety of back grinding conditions. Symbols represent the means and standard deviation limits of at least 10 strength measurements for each geometry in each grinding condition. The uniaxial strengths were measured for dies in the minimum strength orientation with striations perpendicular to the long edge, $\theta = 90^\circ$. The biaxial strengths were measured with 32 mm \times 32 mm square coupons cut from the same wafers as the uniaxial test dies. The back faces of the coupons exhibited parallel arrays of grinding striations; the group of test coupons from a selected

grinding condition included all array orientations relative to the square edges. The square coupons were tested in flat-on-three-ball flexure, which placed the ground back face center of the coupon in equibiaxial stress, significantly greater at the center of the coupon than the edges and thereby largely preventing edge flaws from controlling coupon strength. As a consequence, biaxial flexure testing enables an assessment of greater strengths associated with smaller surface flaws in the center of the coupon. Details of biaxial strength testing can be found elsewhere [Cook, 2017].

In order to minimize interference from edge flaws in the creation of strength degradation plots, early studies of brittle ceramic strengths [Cook *et al.*, 1985] took advantage of the biaxial flexure geometry to extend the domain of introduced strength-controlling indentation flaws to very small contact loads. Similarly motivated application of the biaxial geometry was used in subsequent indentation-strength measurements of Si [Cook, 2006]. The geometry also enabled crystallographic striation-controlled Si strength measurements [McGuire *et al.*, 1997; Chae *et al.*, 2010] and strength measurements of entire wafers [Jeong *et al.*, 2004; Funke *et al.*, 2004]. Other studies have focused on the ability of combined application of uniaxial and biaxial strength testing geometries to separate edge and surface flaw populations [Cotterell *et al.*, 2003; Zhao *et al.*, 2009] and this is the intent here in Fig. 9. The mean biaxial strengths in Fig. 9 are consistently about 1.5 times greater than the matching mean uniaxial strengths, with somewhat greater biaxial strength dispersion. Strength in the equibiaxial test geometry is controlled by the largest surface flaw in the stressed central region, independent of flaw or striation orientation relative to the coupon edge. Hence, the implication of Fig. 9 is that strength controlling surface flaws generated by a variety of grinding conditions are smaller and slightly more variable in size than $\theta = 90^\circ$ edge flaws. This finding extends to polished dies and coupons, in which visible grinding striations are absent. The small increase in mean strength and increased strength dispersion for biaxial strengths relative to uniaxial strengths imply that clear distinction between surface and edge flaw populations is difficult for $\theta = 90^\circ$ or random θ uniaxial die orientations, consistent with previous observations [Cotterell *et al.*, 2003; Zhao *et al.*, 2009]. Comparison of Figs. 8 and 9 suggest that distinction between surface and edge flaw populations for the much greater strength $\theta = 0^\circ$ dies is likely although $\theta = 0^\circ$ dies also exhibit great strength dispersion.

As applied stress conditions in the center of a loaded square coupon are equibiaxial, the strength controlling nature of surface flaws associated with striations should not depend significantly on striation orientation relative to coupon edges. Hence, biaxial strength should be invariant with test coupon position on a wafer. Figure 10 shows a plot of relative biaxial strength as a function of coupon radial location for several Z1 + Z2 ground 200 mm wafers. In order to compare radial variations between grinding conditions, the strengths are normalized by the maximum observed for each condition. Symbols represent individual strength measurements.

Different symbols represent different wafers. Radial location is measured from wafer center. Although there is considerable dispersion, consistent with Fig. 9, the majority of strengths fall between 0.6 and 0.8 of the maximum observed for each wafer, as indicated by the shaded band and consistent with the earlier observations [McGuire *et al.*, 1997]. Slightly greater strengths were observed for coupons from locations closer to the wafer center, suggesting a slight radial dependence to the grinding process, perhaps associated with chuck shape or grinding wheel or spindle tilt [Chidambaram *et al.*, 2003a; Sun *et al.*, 2005ab].

Figure 10. Plot of biaxial strengths of back face ground Si dies as a function of die radial location relative to wafer center. Different symbols represent dies sampled from different ground wafers. The strengths are normalized to the greatest strength observed for each wafer. The shaded band is a guide to the eye.

A major motivation for the work here, considered in a final experimental observation, is that of grinding striation orientation effects on the loads supported by packaged dies. Figure 11 shows an empirical distribution function (edf) of the failure loads of ground packaged dies. Packaging consisted of die attachment to a metal lead frame and sealing in a polymer encapsulant. The failure loads were determined by deforming the packaged dies at constant rate in uniaxial three point bending with the die ground faces in tension and recording the peak supported loads. The edf is bimodal, consisting of a number of small-load failures, separation, and a number of large-load failures. Example experimental load-displacement responses are shown in the inset. The large load failures (bold line) were characterized by linearly increasing load-displacement responses until peak loads were reached at which the supported loads abruptly decreased to zero and the packages and included dies were separated into two pieces. The small

load failures (fine line) were characterized by similarly sloped increasing load-displacement responses until smaller peak loads were reached that were followed by small load drops and re-loads until large large load drops to a non-zero loads. Displacement continued at these intermediate loads until eventual slow load drops to zero load at which point the packages were intact but plastically deformed and the internal dies were broken. All dies were depackaged after mechanical testing by dissolving the polymer encapsulant and the back faces subsequently inspected. In all cases, the small load failures were associated with striations perpendicular to the die long axes and the large load failures were associated with striations parallel to the die long axes, indicated in the schematic diagrams.

Figure 11. Empirical distribution function (edf) of failure loads for packaged devices containing back face ground Si dies. The edf is bimodal, consisting of weak packages containing dies with back face grinding striations perpendicular to the die long axis and strong packages containing dies with back face grinding striations parallel to the die long axis. The inset shows the observed load-displacement behavior.

Figure 11 makes clear that the above considerations regarding wafer back grinding and the consequent effects of striation orientation on die strength are critical in determining finished device performance and reliability. The next section develops a model to predict die strength as a function of wafer grinding parameters.

4. Grinding controlled strength model

4.1. Analysis

Figure 12 is a plan view diagram of in-feed grinding of a wafer back face, similar to the diagram shown earlier [Mendelson et al., 1999, 2001] and slightly different from that used in a later model [Chidambaram, 2003b]. The wafer is fixed in an XY coordinate system with radius w and front face edge exclusion e . The rectangular dies are of edge lengths s_x and s_y , taken such that the long edge s_y is parallel to Y . A specific die is characterized by center coordinates (c_x, c_y) in XY such that

$$(|c_x| + s_x/2)^2 + (|c_y| + s_y/2)^2 \leq (w - e)^2. \quad (2)$$

An example is indicated by the open dot symbol in Fig. 12.

Figure 12. Plan view diagram of an in feed wafer back grinding process, illustrating the key dimensions and angles used in developing a die strength model. The wafer is the large circle, the grinding wheel is the small circle, and a representative die is shown shaded.

A grinding wheel, radius g , is passed over the wafer such that the grinding wheel center, indicated by the solid dot, describes a circular path relative to the wafer center (the grinding wheel is rotating about its own center). The grinding wheel center path is constrained to radius g such that the grinding wheel periphery passes through the wafer center, as shown in Fig. 12. The constraint leads to an invariant isosceles triangle of points formed by the wafer center, the grinding wheel center, and the intersection of the wafer and grinding wheel peripheries. The triangle thus rotates with the grinding wheel and an example position is shown in Fig. 12, along with the invariant angles θ_g and θ_w characterizing the triangle, given by

$$\cos\theta_g = w/2g \quad (3)$$

and $\theta_w = \pi - 2\theta_g$. The grinding wheel center path is described by the variable angle α , such that the grinding wheel center coordinates (g_x, g_y) in XY are given by

$$g_x = g\cos\alpha, \quad (4a)$$

$$g_y = g\sin\alpha. \quad (4b)$$

The angle α , measured in a conventional anti-clockwise sense as shown in Fig. 12, increases linearly with time as the grinding wheel center moves in the circular path about the wafer center. The grinding wheel trailing periphery thus rotates about the wafer center, generating circular striation arcs radiating from the wafer center as shown in Fig. 5(a). The points (x, y) along such arcs, for general values of α describing the grinding wheel position, are described by

$$(x - g_x)^2 + (y - g_y)^2 = g^2, \quad (5)$$

where (g_x, g_y) are given by Eq. (4).

The α values of interest here are those for which a striation arc passes through the center of a specific die (c_x, c_y) . As the dies are small relative to the wafer and grinding wheel dimensions, the striations on the back face of a die are well approximated by a parallel array of striations tangent to such a center striation. The discrete value of α characterizing the striation passing through a specific die center is obtained by setting $(x, y) = (c_x, c_y)$ and determining α in Eq. (4) such that Eq. (5) is satisfied. Such determination is easily made by first defining the angle $\theta_c = \tan^{-1}(c_y/c_x)$ characterizing the die position (note that this definition differs from that used earlier [Mendelson *et al.*, 1999, 2001]) and second, by recognizing from inspection of Fig. 12 that the upper bound to α is given by $\theta_c + \pi/2 > \theta_g + \alpha$. Simple numerical search can then determine α and thus (g_x, g_y) from Eq. (4) and thence the (x, y) arc from Eq. (5). The derivative along the arc, dy/dx from Eq. (5), is $dy/dx = -(x - g_x)/(y - g_y)$. Hence the orientation θ of the strength-controlling striations on the die back face is given by

$$\tan\theta = (c_y - g_y)/(c_x - g_x). \quad (6)$$

Once θ is determined for a die from implementation of Eqs. (3) to (6), the die strength can be determined from Eq. (1).

4.2. Results

Figure 13 is a diagram of an in-feed ground wafer simulated using the above analysis. The system dimensions were: wafer radius $w = 100$ mm, edge exclusion $e = 3$ mm, die size $s_x \times s_y = 10$ mm \times 16 mm, and grinding wheel radius $g = 70$ mm. The diagram is to scale with dimensions given in mm. The wafer edge and edge exclusion boundary are shown as the large bold circles. The edges of the 156 dies meeting the constraint of Eq. (2) are shown as the solid rectangular outlines; the centers of such dies are shown as solid dotted symbols. The circular arcs that pass through the centers of the dies, determined from Eqs. (3) to (6), are shown as fine lines.

Figure 13. Mechanical strength map resulting from simulation of a back ground wafer. The front face edge exclusion and die outlines are shown in yellow. The back face grinding striations that pass through the centers of dies are shown in blue. Strong dies are colored green, weak dies are colored red. Dimensions in mm.

Figure 14 shows the edf $Pr(\theta)$ for the striation angles at the center of each die resulting from Fig. 13. The edf forms a straight line across the entire angle domain, indicating that the striation angles result from a uniform probability density. Other simulations (not shown) using smaller die dimensions confirmed this behavior and showed that the deviations from ideal linear behavior in Fig. 14 resulted from discrete non-zero die size. The key implication from Fig. 14 is that as the striation orientation distribution density is uniform, any consequent strength distribution is dependent entirely on the strength-orientation relationship and any perturbations from that relationship arising from experimental or sampling effects.

Figure 14. Empirical distribution function (edf) of center striation orientation angles for the back face ground wafer and dies in Fig. 13. The linear behavior indicates a uniform distribution of angles.

Figure 15 shows whole-wafer strength edf predictions using the orientation edf of Fig. 14, the strength-orientation function of Eq. (1), and the strength parameters describing the Z1 and Z1 + Z2 strengths of Fig. 8. As anticipated above, the strength edf responses are simply rotated, discrete versions of the solid lines shown in Fig. 8. Each response consists of 156 points, each point representing the uniaxial strength of a single die. The edf responses increase in strength from Z1 (left) to Z1 + Z2, g [center, grit study, Fig. 8(b)] to Z1 + Z2, d [right, depth study, Fig. 8(a)]. In all cases, the edfs exhibit near-linear responses at the center of the strength domain and near-vertical responses adjacent to the upper and lower strength bounds. This behavior is quite distinct from the strength edf behavior observed for most other materials. Bulk ceramics, Si MEMS components, brittle particles, glass fibers, and Si nanowires [Cook and DelRio, 2019ab] overwhelmingly exhibit near-horizontal responses adjacent to the upper and lower strength bounds. That is, for most other materials the strength edf is classically sigmoidal.

Particles can often exhibit concave strength edf responses, but the slopes at the bounds are clearly finite [Cook, 2020]. In addition, the strength edf domains in Fig. 15 for Si die failure are wider than those of conventional materials, such as ceramics, glasses, and MEMS, which typically exhibit $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{\min}$ ratios of approximately 2. Particles can exhibit $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{\min}$ ratios of 4 or greater. The strength domains in Fig. 15 (derived from Fig. 8) exhibit $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{\min}$ ratios of approximately 3. Although detailed consideration is beyond the scope of this work, it appears that the distributions of die strengths, reflecting a single type of flaw/die, have much in common with particle strength distributions, reflecting a single flaw/particle. Multiple flaws/specimen in conventional materials give rise to extreme value effects that contract strength distribution domains and lead to sigmoidal features in strength edfs. Here and in particles the single flaw/specimen removes extreme value effects giving rise to broad distributions that reflect the entire flaw population (here, the entire wafer). Further inspection of Fig. 15 shows that the discrete deviations from the overall response are identical for the three grinding conditions (symbols for Z1 and Z1 +Z2, g; solid line for Z1 + Z2, d). As the same wafer-level orientation edf (Fig. 14) was used in strength edf determinations, the deviations from smooth responses arising from the set of discrete orientations is the same for all grinding conditions.

Figure 15. Empirical distribution functions (edf)s for strength behavior of dies from back face ground wafers. Z1 grinding generates the weakest strength dies. Z1 +Z2 grinding generates dies with greater strengths. The edf shapes are atypical for brittle materials.

A final point to note from Fig. 15 is the effect of systematic uncertainty in strength measurement. Fig. 8 shows dispersions in strength about the mean $\sigma(\theta)$ behavior given by Eq. (1) reflecting such uncertainty. The solid line in Fig. 15 shows the mean Z1 + Z2, d strength edf determined assuming no dispersion; it is identical in shape to the Z1 and Z1 + Z2, g edf curves indicated by the solid symbols. The open symbols in Fig. 15 show a Z1 + Z2, d strength edf including dispersion. This edf was calculated by assuming a $\pm 10\%$ uniform variation about the mean value and re-ranking the resultant strengths. The process mimics experimental uncertainty or “scatter.” The effect on the edf is minor; the randomized edf is slightly broader than the original and exhibits small deviations, but is otherwise not very noticeably different. Other simulations (not shown) indicate that even greater uncertainty leads to similar small effects. The re-ranking process smooths out most of the deviations by interchanging opposing strength deviations, leading to little change from the mean response.

The die strengths from the Z1 + Z2, d simulation of Fig. 15 are replotted in Fig. 16 as a function of die radial position relative to the wafer center. The full domain of strengths is observed at all radii and there is no variation in strength with radial position. The same die strength information is replotted in Fig. 13 using radial and angular position—green for the strongest 1/3 of dies and red for the weakest 1/3 of dies. It is clear that there is a significant variation in strength with angular position. Quadrants of the wafer alternate between strong dies (quadrants 1 and 3) and weak dies (quadrants 2 and 4). Figure 15 provides the mechanical strength wafer “map” advocated in the Introduction.

Figure 16. Plot of uniaxial strength of back face ground dies vs position on wafer quantified in terms of radius from wafer center. There is no significant effect of radial position.

Figure 17. Empirical distribution functions (edf)s for strength of dies from a Z1 + Z2 back face ground wafer. The solid line is the strength edf for the entire wafer. The solid and open symbols are edf responses for dies sampled from different angular quadrants (same color scheme as Fig. 13) illustrating the significant effect on strength.

The angular effect is considered in greater quantitative detail in [Fig. 17](#), which shows strength edf behavior for dies selected using the wafer map information of Fig. 13. The solid line in Fig. 17 is the strength edf behavior of the entire ensemble of dies from the wafer (reproducing the open symbol response from Fig. 15). The open and filled symbols in Fig. 17 form strength edf responses of dies selected from the same ensemble but restricted to quadrants 1 and 3 or quadrants 2 and 4, respectively. There are clear differences arising from angular selection. The dies selected from the odd numbered quadrants are stronger and the strength distribution is convex. In contrast, dies selected from the even numbered quadrants are weaker and the strength distribution is concave. Dies selected from quadrants 1 and 3 have a median strength about twice that of dies selected from quadrants 2 and 4.

A clear implication from Fig. 17, reinforcing the mechanical map concept, is that die selection by angular position from a back ground wafer provides an opportunity for optimized mechanical performance of packaged devices. Selected high strength dies could be placed in greater stress packages, *e.g.*, on polymer substrates rather than ceramic substrates, or in applications requiring greater reliability, *e.g.*, in automobiles rather than game consoles. A related implication is that die selection from a mechanical map provides an opportunity for optimized

commercial performance, as dies from an entire wafer can be utilized in appropriate packages and applications. Conversely, Fig. 17 provides a clear warning that angularly selected dies could provide a misleading representation of the mechanical performance of a wafer. The greatest danger is that a few angularly selected (*e.g.*, quadrant 1) dies are selected and tested, exhibiting strengths greater than the wafer as a whole. Device processing decisions regarding back grinding and packaging would then be made based on erroneous, overestimated, strengths. Conversely, random selection from the entire wafer, even in the presence of strength uncertainty, would provide an accurate, if less precise, estimate of die behavior. **Figure 18** reproduces the solid line from Fig. 17 as the strength edf behavior of the entire ensemble of 156 dies from the wafer. The symbols in Fig. 18 form the strength edf responses of 30 dies sampled at random from the ensemble; the three different symbols represent three different samples. Although there are deviations from the ensemble response, the edf responses of the samples exhibit the same domains and medians as the ensemble and would provide accurate guidance for grinding and packaging optimization.

Figure 18. Empirical distribution functions (edf)s for strength of dies from a Z1 + Z2 back face ground wafer. The solid line is the strength edf for the entire wafer. The symbols are edf responses for 30 dies sampled at random from the wafer; different symbols represent separate samples.

5. Summary

A method for generating wafer maps of semiconductor device die strengths was developed. The strength maps are in close analogy with the maps of device electrical performance generated after wafer front face processing. In contrast, the strength maps are based on wafer back face mechanical processing parameters, specifically those characterizing wafer grinding, although are related to the front face parameters of die size and location. A common method of wafer back face processing—in-feed grinding—was considered in detail, and a brief overview of prior observations and analyses of in-feed grinding of Si was presented. In-feed grinding generates wafer back face striations in the form of radiating circular arcs that lead to parallel arrays of striations on die back faces. For the common loading configuration of bending a rectangular die, the striation array orientation relative to the die long axis is a major factor in controlling die strength. Controlled indentation flaw and sharp scratch observations and strength measurements of Si showed that strength controlling striations were most likely sub-threshold linear contact flaws formed by abrasive particles contacting the wafer back face with normal loads less than 0.1 N, less than the weight of a Si wafer. Strength measurements of ground dies showed a significant dependence on striation scale and orientation and with loading geometry; for the most common rectangular die loading configuration, uniaxial strength decreased by a factor of three for grinding striations perpendicular to the die long axis relative to striations parallel to the axis. Coarse grinding decreased strengths at all orientations and strengths measured in biaxial loading were greater than those measured in uniaxial loading (as in bending). A simple cubic expression was used to describe the smooth variation of die mean strength with striation orientation. This expression and the strength bounds were used in a model of die strength based on grinding geometry parameters. The model was implemented numerically and used to generate wafer mechanical maps and die strength distributions—both the maps and the distributions are practical for direct engineering application. The model provides a rare example of “forward” strength distribution analysis, in which the flaw distribution, here the orientation distribution, and the strength dependence, here the cubic expression, are known. Such knowledge enables sample strength distributions to be predicted from population properties, here wafer properties. Examples of the effects of grinding severity, experimental uncertainty, radial position, and angular selection were demonstrated. (“Backward” strength distribution analyses, in which population characteristic are inferred from sample strength distributions, are far more common.) The model is easily extended to other grinding geometries and provides a foundation for consideration of other strength-controlling flaws, such as those generated by dicing of full thickness wafers.

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